

STYLISTIC PECULARITIES. THEMES OF REVENGE AND TRIUMPHANT LOVE IN BRONTE'S "WUTHERING HEIGHTS"

Kholikulova Munisa Abdumalik kizi

Annotation: Few debut novels have aroused as much controversy as Wuthering Heights based on themes, style or on techniques. Although, Wuthering Heights scandalized and nauseated the Victorians, modern critics, nevertheless, speak highly of the strength of the novel's structure and on Emily Bronte's dynamic and disciplined handling of language. A novel comes into existence through the creativity of the writer. And the readers come in contact with the fictional world of the novels through its language. Hence, for comprehending fictional texts, a close study and analysis of language is a necessary prerequisite. Stylistic analysis is used as an analytical tool to see textual patterns and its significance. It is based on statistical data that validate how language, vocabulary and syntax are used to bring about interpretation of the text. Wuthering Heights presents a variety of styles. Stylistically, much ahead of her time, Bronte culled a form best suited to articulate her subject and ideas effectively. This paper is, therefore, an attempt to discover what is striking about Bronte's narrative style.

Keywords: Emily Bronte, Wuthering Heights, Stylistic analysis

INTRODUCTION

Few debut novels have aroused as much controversy as Wuthering Heights based on themes, style or on techniques. The fact that Wuthering Heights, on its promulgation had been deemed as 'coarse', 'immoral', and 'unwomanly', in itself testifies that it deserves serious critical deliberation¹. Wuthering Heights

¹Emily Bronte. Wuthering Heights. 1992. Hertfordshire:Wordsworth, 2000.

scandalized and nauseated the Victorians. ‘Brutal’, ‘disagreeable’ and ‘diabolical’ have been some of the adjectives lavished on it by the early reviewers. Modern critics, nevertheless, speak highly of the strength of the novel’s structure and on Emily Bronte’s dynamic and disciplined handling of language. Stylistically, much ahead of her time, Bronte culled a form best suited to articulate her subject and ideas effectively. In fact, Mark Schorer praises *Wuthering Heights* as, –one of the most carefully constructed novels in the language

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wuthering Heights presents a variety of styles ranging from Catherine’s poetic discourse, Heathcliff’s verbal violence, Lockwood’s superior literary tone and fashionable cliché, Nelly’s homiletic rhetoric to Joseph’s biblical Yorkshire dialect and unintelligible muttering—all producing an interplay of accents and idioms, giving rise to what Bakhtin terms as—dialogical heteroglossia². However, the single most distinctive feature of *Wuthering Heights* is its dialogue with Bronte’s emphasis on personal idiolect. To make this possible she dismantles language in order to make the language of social behaviour in her fictional world intelligible to her readers. Consequently, the diction used by various characters reveals their speech style. But although a skilled craftswoman, Bronte, desists from ornate verbal display. Her linguistic style depends largely on her admirable choice of words, though it is marked by hyperbolic excess especially in the dramatic speeches of Catherine and Heathcliff. The directness of Bronte’s style is amply demonstrated in the very opening paragraphs of Chapter one in the novel. This is one of the innumerable examples of the direct method of introducing movement by means of extra accent upon certain focusing words. Each sentence goes straight as a dart to the impression sought to be conveyed

² David Lodge. *Language of Fiction—Essays in Criticism and Verbal Analysis of the English Novel*. (1966). London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1984.

(Allot 143):

Pure bracing ventilation they must have up there at all times, indeed one may guess the power of the north wind blowing over the edge, by the excessive slant of a few stunted firs at the end of the house; and by a range of gaunt thorns all stretching their limbs one way, as if craving alms of the sun (2).

The paragraph conveys a vivid impression of the way the wind blows up on the heights. Similarly, Lockwood's entry into the interior of the house is matched exactly with the action it describes. –One step brought us into the family sitting-room, without any introductory lobby or passage' (2).

On closer analysis, one discovers that the most distinctive single trait in Emily Bronte's narrative style is repetition. Everything in the novel is a kind of double. There are not only verbal repetitions, but the plot, structure, narrators, and the characters themselves form a double to each other. There are even two diary accounts, Catherine's diary forming a kind of inner text to Lockwood's diary which forms the outer text. Most of the repeated words in the text are content words (Noun, Verb, Adjective and their derivatives). Words repeated tend to stick longer in the mind. But repetition is confined not only to words or sentences but extends to include even ideas (images) that express the theme(s) of the novel.

At the lexical level, the very texture of language, i.e., vocabulary is examined. Emily Bronte's range of diction is remarkable. Stevie Davies, in fact, elucidates that the copious and literary vocabulary in the novel is founded in a pithy Anglo-Saxon- derived lexis and that the vocabulary is often Latinated and polysyllabic (1998:100-101). One is introduced to Wuthering Heights first through the filter of Lockwood's language. The most distinctive feature in Lockwood's speeches is its 'literariness'. It is stilted, pompous, mannered, 'bookish' and riddled with clichés. Besides, he uses hackneyed and affected language, like in his description of his sea- side flirtation with –a most fascinating

creature--a real goddess' (3) who was also a -poor innocent³. Further, he speaks of Cathy as Heathcliff's -amiable lady', then of Hareton as the -favoured possessor of the beneficent fairy' (9). Taking Cathy to be Hareton's wife, he fantasizes himself to be a possible seducer of Cathy. -She has thrown herself away upon that boor from sheer ignorance that better individuals existed! A sad pity...I must beware how I make her regret her choice' (8). However, Lockwood's narration presents a conflict between the literary genre and the social reality the narrative has moved into; the chasm between his mannered literary language and the domestic reality at the Heights.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, *Wuthering Heights* presents a plurality of styles. Language in the novel is full of contradictions. The specific tensions and paradoxes built into linguistic patterns are noticeable in the word- structure and sentence -structure which lend complexity and richness to the text. What is remarkable in Bronte's lexicon is the striking use of her verbs. It is full of violent movement and conflict and has momentum and energy as evident even in the speeches of her characters. Words wreck vocal violence and since her characters carry the unmediated emotions of childhood into their adult lives, they are forever bickering; quarrel being the favoured mode of communication. The characters and their environment are presented through appropriate diction. *Wuthering Heights* is described as a place which experiences 'atmospheric tumult'. Further, even those passages of excessive emotion are controlled stylistically by breaks from past to present tense, interjected remarks, by broken phrases, and half-expressed ideas which reveal the psychological state of her characters. In addition the sparse but vivid description gives the text a highly emotive texture. Apart from these, her powerful imagery also helps to make her work truly idiosyncratic.

³ Steve Davies. Emily Bronte. U.K: Northcote House Publishers Ltd, 1998.

REFERENCES

- [1] Emily Bronte. *Wuthering Heights*. 1992. Hertfordshire:Wordsworth, 2000.
- [2] David Lodge. *Language of Fiction-Essays in Criticism and Verbal Analysis of the English Novel*. (1966). London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1984.
- [3] G. N Leech and Mick Short. *Style in Fiction*. London: Longman, 1981.
- [4] Northrop Frye. -Myth, Fiction and Displacement’ (1961) in *Literary Criticism: A Reading*. (ed.) B. Das and Jitendra Mohanty. Calcutta: Oxford UP, 1985.
- [5] Nicholas Marsh. *Emily Bronte - Wuthering Heights*. London: Macmillan, 1999.
- [6] Steve Davies. *Emily Bronte*. U.K: Northcote House Publishers Ltd, 1998.
- [7] Thomas A. Volger. (ed.) -20th Century Interpretations of *Wuthering Heights*’ in *Wuthering Heights : A Collection of Critical Essays*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc, 1968.